

An Enquiry into the Jaina Concept of Reality and its Comparison with the Ideas of the so-called Brahminical Religious Texts

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Abstract

Jainism and the so called Brahminical religion (popularly called Hinduism) both are one of the most ancient religions of India. They both originated in the soil of India. As a result, they both have some similarities in common. But they have some dissimilarities. This article would discuss about them.

Keywords

Jainism, Brahminical, Religion, Karma, Dharma

Jainism is one of the religions that originated in the land of India and contributed to its culture and philosophy in many ways. The antiquity of this religion is much debated. Scholars like A.N. Upadhye argue that the antiquity of this religion goes back to prehistoric times. (Upadhye 1975) But to support this claim, not enough archaeological evidence is available. A common consensus among scholars is that this religion flourished during the 6th Century CE along with Buddhism. But the origin of this religion is much older. In the words of Upinder Singh we can safely say, “The Jaina doctrine is much older than the Buddhist one, but it is difficult to say precisely how old it is. The Buddha and Mahavira were contemporaries and there are some similarities between their teachings, for instance in their rejection of the authority of the Veda, their non-theistic doctrine, emphasis on renunciation and human effort as a means to attaining salvation, and establishment of a monastic order for men and women. However, there are also several marked differences in their philosophical ideas”. (Singh 2020) Now, the thought of so called Brahminical religious texts (corpus of Vedas, Upanishads, Bhagavad Gita and other texts) which would convey the highest philosophical understanding, had certain similarities and dissimilarities with Jaina school of thought. This paper would investigate into this matter.

If we want to get a glimpse of Jaina philosophy, we can go through the following passage:

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“The Jaina criticism of other philosophical systems is that their pronouncements about reality—for instance, on whether reality is eternal or non-eternal, changing or unchanging—represent a single (ekanta), partial, and extreme view of things. The views of other schools are not condemned as absolutely invalid but as partially true statements (nayas), which cannot lay claim to absolute validity. Jaina doctrine insists that reality is manifold (anekanta) (see Jaini [1979], 2001 for details of Jaina doctrines). Everything that exists (sat, i.e., being) has three aspects—substance (dravya), quality (guna), and mode (pariyaya). The Jaina doctrine of anekantavada (doctrine of the manifold nature of reality) holds that reality is very complex and has multiple aspects. The doctrines of anekantavada and syadavada (the doctrine of maybe) emphasize the relativity of all knowledge. According to syadavada, every judgement we make is relative to the particular aspect of the object we are judging and the point of view from which we judge it. No judgement is true without qualification. The essential point behind syadavada and anekantavada is that reality cannot be grasped in its entirety and complexity. All that is possible are a number of partially true statements about it. Every statement about reality should be prefixed with the word syat (‘maybe’, or more appropriately in this context, ‘in some respect’). Another word that is added to all such statements is eva (in fact). Together, the words syat and eva, added to all statements, emphasize that such statements refer only to a particular aspect of reality from a particular perspective. So, with the addition of ‘syateva’, the statement that the jiva (soul) is eternal would be accepted as partially true from a certain point of view. But the statement that the jiva is not eternal, preceded with the words syateva, would also be accepted as partially true from another point of view. Every statement about any aspect of reality is conditional on four factors—the specific being (sva-dravya), specific location (sva-kshetra), specific time (sva-kala), and the specific state (sva-bhava) of the thing that is being spoken of. These ideas are further developed to construct the theory of sapta-bhangi-naya (the seven-fold nayas). Existent reality consists of three basic categories—sentient (i.e., that which has consciousness), material, and neither sentient nor material. The sentient category is represented by the jiva (variously translated as sentient essence, life monad, or soul). Matter is the second category and is made of aggregates of atoms (pudgala), which have form, colour, taste, and smell, and can be touched and felt. The third category is known as arupi-ajiva. It includes four substances (dravya)—space (akasha), the principle of motion (dharma), the principle of rest (adharma), and time (kala).” (Singh 2020)

Now, if we examine the doctrine of the Vedas, Upanishads and Bhagavad Gita we can find some similarities. In the 1st Mandala of Rig Veda, 164th Sukta, 46th Mantra it is said:

‘EkamSadviprāBahudhā Vadanti’ meaning the truth is one but the learned people define it in many different ways. It seems similar to the concept of *anekantavada* in the way that one truth or reality might have many aspects. However, the concept of *dharma* is different. In the so-called Brahminical religious texts, the word *Dharma* stands for righteousness and one’s own duties and as we have seen in Jainism it stands for the principle of motion.

The Jains have the concept of an eternal universe divided into infinite number of cycles, *utsarpini* (period of improvement) and *avasarpini* (period of decline). In so called Brahminical religion there is also a concept of four *yugas*, each being worse than the previous. But in the words of A.L. Basham, “Unlike the cosmology of the Buddhists and Hindus, that of the Jainas involves no cataclysms of universal destruction.” (Basham 1954)

Both in Jainism and the so-called Brahminical religion there are concepts of *Kalpa Vriksha*, the wish-fulfilling tree.

There is a concept of *nyavada* in Jainism:

“The object of knowledge, thus, is highly complex; it consists of substances, qualities, and modifications; it is extended over three times (past, present, and future) and infinite space; and it is simultaneously subjected to origination, permanence, and destruction. It can be fully known only in omniscience (*kevala-jnāna*), which is not possessed by ordinary human beings who perceive through their organs of sense. What they know is only partial; they are like blind men who touch some part or other of an elephant and variously describe it as a fan, a pillar, a snake, etc. Thus, the apprehension of an ordinary human being is partial, and therefore valid only from a particular point of view. This is what is called *nayavāda* in Jainism.” (Upadhye 1975)

This concept of elephant felt by different blind persons can be found in both Buddhism and Hindu texts.

However, the Jaina concept of *Karma* is much different from that of Brahminical religion: “Jaina philosophy conceives of an infinite number of *jivas*. The *jiva* does not have a form of its own. In the way in which light from a lamp fills up a room, it acquires the size and form of the body it inhabits and becomes co-extensive with it. The *jiva* has three main qualities—consciousness (*chaitanya*), bliss (*sukha*), and energy (*virya*). Jaina doctrine holds that *jivas* transmigrate due to *karma*, but its ideas of transmigration and *karma* are unique. *Karma* is understood as consisting of material particles floating about in space. *Karmic matter* is of different kinds; some have a directly negative effect on the *jiva*, others do not. The major culprits are the *mohaniya* (delusion-causing) *karmas*. The *karma* particles obscure and obstruct

the consciousness, bliss, and energy of the jiva, in the in which dust mars the reflective power of a mirror. The karma particles are attracted towards the jiva due to its association with the passions, desire, and hatred. The state when the karma particles actually begin to flow towards the jiva to bind it is known as asrava (flow). A jiva associated with karma particles is considered to be a jiva in bondage (bandha). Some jivas have an important quality known as bhavyatva—the capability of becoming free—that does not get affected or overwhelmed by the karma particles. By exertion and right knowledge, the influx of fresh karma can be stopped (samvara). The next stage is that of nirjara (wearing out). In successive stages, though a transformation of consciousness and behaviour, the jiva can move from bondage to liberation. When the last karma particle has moved away from the jiva, ignorance disappears, and it is restored to its omniscient, ideal state. The cycle of samsara is broken and moksha is attained. The ladder leading from ignorance to omniscience is visualized as having 14 rungs or stages of purification called gunasthanas. One who has entered the 13th stage of kevalajnana is known as an arhat. An arhat who has also already acquired the capability of teaching the doctrine is known as a tirthankara. The 14th stage is achieved by an arhat immediately before his death, when he is liberated from all activity and from the last few remaining karma particles. The final abode of liberated souls is a world called siddha-loka.” (Singh 2020)

However, in Brahminical religion the concept of Karma is different. It refers to the the universal law of cause and effect, meaning every action (physical, mental, verbal) has consequences, shaping one's destiny and cycle of rebirth.

Thus, Jainism and the Brahminical religion have many similarities and dissimilarities.

Bibliography

- Singh, Upinder. *A History of ancient and Early medieval India: From the stone age to the 12th century (PB)*. Pearson Education India, 2020.
- Basham, A. L. *The wonder that was India*. London.Grove Press, INC. New York.1959.
- Upadhye, A.N. Jainism (pp. 100 to 110), Basham, Arthur Llewellyn,eds. *A cultural history of India*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press, 1975.
- Ranganathananda, Swami. *The message of the Upanishads*. Advaita Ashrama (A Publication House of Ramakrishna Math, Belur Math), 1971.